

Stranger to the Trees

Kat Austen

#trees #microplastic #coexistence

[Project teaser](#)

The multimedia project **Stranger to the Trees** explores the complementary coexistence of microplastics and trees as carbon sinks. How do trees and microplastics coexist in forests, capturing carbon in the time of the climate crisis? Combining video, interactive sound and sculpture, *Stranger to the Trees* queries the response of forest ecosystems to the ubiquitous and irrevocable dispersal of microplastics around the Earth.

What we consider to be our environment unequivocally and ubiquitously contains plastic. Plastics have been found to be present even at the outskirts of human reach: at the bottom of the Mariana trench, in the rain, clouds and atmosphere. While plastic can be detrimental to the quality of an ecosystem, plastic pollution is also a carbon sink, storing carbon and keeping carbon dioxide and methane out of the atmosphere. But is this carbon sink, itself an embodiment of industrial processes that contribute to the climate crisis, in competition or complementarity to forests? By what processes will they become together?

This project builds on ongoing artistic research by Dr Kat Austen (UK/DE) on the topics of microplastic and the climate crisis. Austen is focussing on the coexistence of birch trees with microplastics and developing artistic and DIY scientific research methods to explore this. The birch is a pioneer species, colonising land disrupted by human, following human and industrial pollution. Not demanding of the soil, birch withstands both full sunlight and low temperatures. These characteristics define the birch as a perfect pioneer in the plastisphere. The artistic research focusses on birch groves in forests between Berlin, Germany and Wroclaw, Poland and will include microscopy and histology of tree parts, field recordings of audio and video from forests where microplastic and trees cohabit to examine the incorporation and rejection between plastics and trees with the constant consideration of the possibility for complementarity and coexistence.

Stranger to the Trees realises in hybrid artistic form the new materiality of forests in the time of ubiquitous human-made plastic pollution.

The **Coral Empathy Device** is an interactive sculptural sound installation that engenders empathy in humans for coral under the influence of anthropogenic environmental factors of plastic and acoustic pollution.

[More information](#)

Credits

Coral Empathy Device was initiated at Pikslo_Deep Dive in Pikel 2015, and its production was supported by Programme for Creativity and Innovation, NYU Shanghai and NYU Shanghai Gallery

The **Matter of the Soul** is a musical and sono-sculptural work exploring human empathy with the process of dispersal in the Arctic. Musical compositions include sounds from instruments made from hacked scientific equipment that measure chemical properties of water. Austen plays Arctic water live using these instruments during performances.

[More information](#)

Credits

Research for *The Matter of the Soul* was carried out during the Artist in the Arctic residency 2017 with Friends of Scott Polar Research Institute. During a residency on the ship the Akademik Sergei Vavilov, sailing through the Canadian High Arctic, Austen made field recordings of the acidity and salinity of Arctic waters using hacked pH and conductivity meters, and conducted interviews. Scientific instruments were donated by the teaching laboratories of the Chemistry Department, UCL. The work was further developed during Austen's Cultural Fellowship in Art and Science at the University of Leeds' Cultural Institute, with additional support from Ice Alive and the Polar Museum.

About Kat Austen

Kat Austen is a person. In her artistic practice, she focusses on environmental issues. She melds disciplines and media, creating sculptural and new media installations, performances and participatory work. Austen's practice is underpinned by extensive research and theory, and driven by a motivation to explore how to move towards a more socially and environmentally just future.

Working from her studio in Berlin, Austen is currently Artist in Residence at WRO Art Center through the EMAP/EMARE programme, Artistic Fellow at IASS Potsdam, Associate at ZeM, Brandenburg, Artist in Residence at the Faculty of Maths and Physical Sciences, University College London and Senior Teaching Fellow at UCL Arts and Sciences. She is a member of the bbk, an inaugural member of the London Creative Network and is co-founder of the DIY Hack the Panke collective in Berlin.

Austen's field research has included a voyage around the Canadian High Arctic as Artist in the Arctic 2017 for Friends of Scott Polar Research Institute (University of Cambridge) for her project The Matter of the Soul. In 2018 Austen was selected as inaugural Cultural Fellow in Art and Science at the Cultural Institute, University of Leeds for the same project. Austen has been awarded residencies internationally, including with NYU Shanghai, ArtOxygen Mumbai, LAs theatre, the Clipperton Project and Utter! Spoken word.

Austen has exhibited at Bonhams Art Gallery, London; The Polar Museum, Cambridge; Kuehlhaus, Berlin, among others, and her work is held internationally in private collections. She has performed around the globe, including at Opera North, Leeds; Fusion Festival, Berlin and Headlands Center for the Arts, San Francisco.

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